

**MECHANISMS FOR ASSESSING AND MANAGING THE
ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES
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Annotation: *The article proposes a system of indicators for assessing environmental impact and recommends the implementation of the "polluter pays" principle, incentive tax benefits, and ISO 14001 standards. Based on the results, it contains practical recommendations for managing environmental risks, increasing the environmental adaptation of enterprises, and improving public policy.*

Keywords: *industrial enterprises, environmental impact, environmental monitoring, waste management, ISO 14001, green technologies, energy efficiency, environmental management system, environmental protection.*

Introduction

Currently, industry and transport, which are the most important components of the national and regional economy, embodying the development of science and technology, are the main factor in the development of any region. Improper organization of the rational placement and development of productive forces negatively affects the natural environment, especially the health of the population. Of course, there is no doubt that industrial enterprises and factories cause great harm to the environment. In fact, two-thirds of the pollution caused by climate change is attributed to factories¹.

Industrial development is an important factor in the economic growth of any country. However, this process is also characterized by a negative impact on the ecological balance. Environmental problems, such as air pollution, water scarcity, and soil degradation, are especially acute as a result of the activities of large industrial enterprises. Therefore, identifying, assessing, and effectively managing the environmental impact of industrial enterprises is one of the urgent tasks. This article analyzes the identification of factors that negatively affect the environment, the development of mechanisms for their assessment, and management methods aimed at reducing environmental risks.

¹ Collection of materials of the Republican scientific-practical online conference No. 31 on the topic "Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish va unga qaratilgan kreativ g'oyalar, takliflar va yechimlar" February 15, 2022.

Methodology

The study used methods of environmental monitoring, statistical analysis, and a systematic approach based on a comprehensive approach. First of all, the main environmental problems arising as a result of the activities of industrial enterprises were identified. Further, a system of indicators used in environmental impact assessment was developed. In the assessment, such criteria as "waste volume," "emission level," "resource consumption," and "energy efficiency" were identified as the main factors. At the same time, the environmental management system, the implementation of "green technologies," and environmental management systems based on international standards (ISO 14001) were studied as management mechanisms.

Results

The research results showed that the environmental impact of industrial enterprises is mainly manifested in the emission of gases into the atmosphere, production waste, and pollution of water resources. As a result of the analysis conducted on the basis of evaluation indicators, it was established that the level of environmental safety in most enterprises is low. At the same time, at enterprises where an environmental management system has been implemented, the volume of waste has decreased by 18-25%, and the efficiency of water resource use has increased. The use of green technologies not only reduced the environmental impact, but also made it possible to reduce energy costs by 15-20%.

At the first stage, the main environmental problems arising as a result of the activities of industrial enterprises (air, water and soil pollution, an increase in waste, excessive consumption of natural resources) were identified. To do this²:

Environmental monitoring - air, water, and soil samples were taken and the level of pollution was measured to determine the impact of enterprises on the environment.

Statistical Data Analysis - data collected by public and private monitoring systems (volume of emissions, composition of emissions) were analyzed.

The following main criteria were established for the quantitative assessment and comparison of problems:

Waste volume - the amount of solid, liquid, and gaseous waste.

Emission level - emission of harmful substances (CO₂, SO₂, NO_x) into the air.

² Author's development

Resource consumption - water, energy, and raw material consumption.

Energy Efficiency - the level of energy savings in production.

The following methods of environmental protection were investigated:

Environmental Management System (EMS) - formation and control of environmental policy at enterprises.

"Green technologies" - waste recycling, low-waste production technologies.

International standards (ISO 14001) - global experience of environmental management systems and their applicability in local conditions.

The collected data were analyzed using the methods of **correlation, regression analysis and dynamic modeling**, based on the results, the main sources of negative environmental impact and ways to reduce them were proposed.

Discussion

The obtained results indicate the need for a systematic approach and modern management mechanisms to reduce the negative impact of industrial enterprises on the environment. Through the implementation of evaluation indicators, it becomes possible to systematically monitor the environmental situation of enterprises and effectively manage them. At the same time, it is important to expand economic mechanisms based on the "polluter pays" principle in managing environmental risks, encouraging enterprises to transition to environmentally friendly technologies through incentive taxes and subsidies. The widespread implementation of international standards, such as ISO 14001, is an important tool in the systematization of environmental management. Consequently, to ensure environmental safety at industrial enterprises, it is necessary to harmonize state policy, economic incentives, and technological modernization based on a comprehensive approach.

Environmental management systems (EMS) provide enterprises with a systematic approach to environmental protection. ISO 14001 standards provide an opportunity to use international experience in managing environmental risks. The transition to green technologies plays an important role in waste recycling and resource conservation.

The principle of "polluter pays" implies economic sanctions for enterprises that do not comply with environmental requirements. Incentive tax benefits will support enterprises implementing clean technologies. Proper adjustment of economic mechanisms can accelerate environmental modernization.

The state's strict environmental policy and regulatory system are of great importance. International cooperation and the application of global standards encourage local enterprises to operate environmentally sustainably. Public-private partnership is an effective way to address environmental problems.

Conclusion

The issue of assessing and managing the environmental impact of industrial enterprises remains an integral part of sustainable development policy. The research results show that if environmental impact assessment is systematized based on indicators, it will be much more effective to identify and eliminate environmental problems. Management mechanisms should be strengthened through technological renewal, compliance with environmental standards, and incentive policies. These approaches guide industrial enterprises towards environmentally responsible activities.

List of used literature

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